

EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES FOR LEARNING SECOND LANGUAGE

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ЭФФЕКТИВНЫЕ СТРАТЕГИИ ИЗУЧЕНИЯ ВТОРОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Abstract: *This article provides detailed information on second language learning techniques, strategies, what we need to achieve by learning a second language, and programs for independent learning.*

Keywords: Foreign, international, online, sites, applications, applicant, professional, cognitive.

Аннотация: *В этой статье представлена подробная информация о методах изучения второго языка, стратегиях, о том, чего нам нужно достичь, изучая второй язык, и о программах для самостоятельного изучения.*

Ключевые слова: *зарубежный, международный, онлайн, сайты, приложения, соискатель, профессиональный.*

Learning a second language and even more languages is not only useful but necessary. International students studying abroad learn their language School abroad is very important. This may seem daunting, but you can easily learn more languages when there are online language learning sites and apps. Unless you are among people who speak their own language, you may not find it helpful to learn a new language, and you will not understand without a language. You will also be proud when you have the opportunity to communicate with people of different nationalities and cultures in their own languages.

There are countless reasons why you should learn a second language, so we'll list the top twenty reasons. Let's show you why we need to learn another language.

Advantages of learning a second language

1. Increases job opportunities
2. Strengthens the brain
3. Improves memory
4. Increases the ability to take on multiple tasks
5. Improves performance in other Academic Fields
6. Opportunity to meet new people
7. It will be easier to learn another language

8. It boosts our confidence
9. This is important
- 10.. Expands our tourism opportunities
11. It improves our first language
- 12.. It enhances understanding in the world
13. Get to know new cultures
14. It is a success in itself
15. Increases the skill of our decision
16. Increases network capacity
17. The brain gets bigger
18. Low risk of dementia and Alzheimer's
19. It helps to stay in tourist areas in the future
20. It enhances our creativity

Here are the benefits of learning a new language in a second.

Have you seen a special job posting about how applicants need to know how to speak a particular language? Yes, there are a lot of them, especially if you hope to find a job outside of your home country. Also, learning a second language opens up a world of career opportunities for us. From a translator to a translator, an educator is all about the job industry.

The world is changing rapidly and many companies are looking to open branches in different corners of the world. Before such companies hire us, we need to be a person who knows another foreign language, has a worldview. Even in companies in our home country, the ability to speak a second language can provide us with employment. Learning a new language is very difficult. It is to follow a whole new complex system of rules, structures, and lectures. So the brain needs to work harder. He must master the complexity of understanding and master new models. Gradually, our brains begin to understand new meanings of words and help you develop communication, knowledge thinking, and problem-solving skills. These skills are useful both personally and professionally.

Learning a second language also implies different communication languages. We do not learn a language that does not interact. Therefore, we use your memory to learn another language effectively. This is because it now provides us with more information on a regular basis and on the basis of fast demand.

A new language requires not only familiarity with words and rules, but also the ability to remember and apply knowledge. And it's about using a new language on a daily basis, taking your brain to the gym. It just gets better and sharper. Being multilingual will speed up your ability to remember names, instructions, facts, and numbers. When we ask for information in different languages of the brain and demand switching languages, we act moderately. Some people also report that the brain has many functions, such as brain magic. Because the brains of the two bilinguals are used to exchange languages, they are more suited to having higher mental abilities. Like editing irrelevant information and focusing on important information. They do a lot of repetition.

Learning a second language leads to higher cognitive skills and consequently improves the student's level of knowledge. Because bilingual students can concentrate and perform more tasks better than their classmates, they are more likely to perform better on standardized tests. They include excellent math, reading and vocabulary, as well as other problem-solving tasks.

You can also meet with the U.S. Department of Education and Culture Important Linguistics Program if you need funding for language learning. If we are someone who loves to meet new people and communicate with them, then learning a new language should be a priority. As we learn new languages, the doors of communication opportunities around the world open up for us. For example, we make new friends immediately by learning in a group setting. If we haven't started trying our new language with the people in the group, we can meet people online. People get along well with us when we talk to our parents. If we successfully learn a second language, it will be easier to learn another language. The methods we use in learning a second language will be handy for another language. As your cognitive process grows, so does our ability to replicate the language learning process with multiple languages.

Our brains learn to identify ways to learn a language and take them in a series of steps. Once you learn a language, our brain understands how it is structured. As a result of understanding the syntax, grammar and sentence structure of the text. We make mistakes when we discover a new language. Some of these mistakes, we make them in front of an audience. This is good for the learning process. The more people you laugh at us for your mistakes, the better we decide to be. So our new language skills will be tested in front of a larger audience. Naturally, we feel that we are stepping out of our comfort zone, and the result is a deep sense of success.

The world is moving forward and now everything is happening on a global scale. If you're hoping to be competitive or appeal to a large audience, you can't stand in one language. Being bilingual is becoming increasingly important. Being able to speak multiple languages is not only a source of pride, but also a confirmation of your relevance in the global community. For example, when you learn to speak Spanish, you enjoy traveling to more than 20 countries where Spanish is the main language. You know exactly how to receive you in a country where you can speak their language. So you will have no problem adding these countries to your travel list.

If you learn a new language, you will understand the simplicity and complexity of your language. This is the result of a natural comparison related to being multilingual. You begin to examine where your language is different from another language. Automatically, in a second language, when you compose sentences in your heart, you interpret them in your native language. So better understand your language. We all want to know the world we live in better. This is the reason for all our readings. We are not satisfied with what we know about our country either. Without knowing about the work of other countries, we do not consider our knowledge to be sufficient. However, we can only know about other countries about our language. That is, when we understand a new language, we take a step to explore the world. You immediately have access to books, movies, television programs

and newspapers of the country that speaks this language. thus you will know the truth of both the history and the culture of the people, of course.

Now that you have seen the benefits of learning a second language, you may already have a desire to learn a second language. Now your next question is where can I learn a new language? The answer is very simple, you can learn languages in educational institutions and online through special websites and applications. There are all sorts of brick buildings where you can learn a new language, but of course it's paid. Most of them can be very expensive. At the same time, your employer does not want to place you on a day off, so you achieve your personal desire to learn a second language.

If you want to study online, you can learn a new language in time. Plus, it saves you a lot of money because some online language learning platforms are free. They also offer you great options. You can choose from beginner and elementary courses, interview courses, and comprehensive courses that will make you fluent. These free courses allow you to decide if you can really spend your time and energy learning a second language.

While it is effective in learning languages, Duolingo is also fun and addictive. This online language learning service approaches learning like a game and offers apps for iOS, Windows Phone and Android. Create a profile to get started. You can then start an introductory course or take a test to move on to an extended course. Duolingo is absolutely free to use.

With Open Culture, you can learn popular languages like English, French, Spanish, Italian, Russian or Mandarin. The online language learning platform has a total of 48 free language course options on the download portal. You can download Persian / Persian, Estonian, Icelandic, Gaelic and many other languages for free in mp3 format for later download and listening.

Livemocha is an online language learning platform that gives you access to free lessons for 35 languages. There is also a live team of native speakers from 190 countries. You can connect with people from the team to put your speech into practice.

Babbel allows you to learn 14 new languages, including English, French, German, Portuguese, Swedish and Turkish. In addition to speaking, these online language learning platforms teach you to speak, read, and write in the language of your choice. Babel also has mobile apps and its introductory courses are free.

Learning a second language can open doors that were previously closed to you. You can enrich your life and business, make new friends, and create better networks to better explore the world while people speak their native language.

The key to language learning is vocabulary, which means that the more vocabulary a student has, the better he or she will understand the information he or she hears or reads, and at the same time will be able to express their thoughts orally and can express color in written speech.

References

1. Anderson NJ. Metacognitive reading strategies increase L2 performance. The Language Teacher. 2003;27:20-22.

2. Bell J. Doing your research project. Open University Press, England; 2010.
3. Chamot AU. Issues in language learning strategy research and teaching. Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching. 2004;1:14-26.
4. Chien KL. An overview of language learning strategies. ARECLS. 2010;7:132-152.
5. Cohen L. Research method in education. Routledge, New York; 2010.